

Editorial: Call for papers- AI Research in Educational Leadership (AIREL)

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EDITORIAL

Artificially intelligent devices or systems that simulate human intelligence to carry out tasks and may constantly enhance themselves depending on the data they gather are moving at an unstoppable pace and have an impact on humanity in many areas, including social life, business life, entertainment style, and trade methods; but they also have the potential to seriously alter education as well as trivialize concepts of time and space, change learning contents and methods, and even inspire revolutions that could potentially change how people perceive education and manage educational organizations entirely. The introduction of AI into everyday life has altered how people acquire information and sustain their academic lives. After breakthrough improvements in technology like AI and XR, the lengthy and often tedious process of human education from stone tablets to computer displays has accelerated dramatically.

Modern education systems can benefit from the widespread usage of AI, which opens up new possibilities (Ouyang & Jiao, 2021), especially in educational management process as AI technology assists and streamlines administrative work, in addition to making it possible to provide lectures beyond borders of geography (Bates vd., 2020). However, in the digital-based innovation process that Technology 5.0 has dragged educational organizations, school administrators and teachers need to be prepared for the new limitations and problems that the new immersive learning environments including AI and XR will bring to the field of education as well as the opportunities. As each new technology enters our living spaces, it creates hope, benefit, and glamour as well as fear, anxiety, and problems in societies. New technologies, while offering an attractive network of new possibilities and opportunities, actually drag us into previously unexplored, uninhabited lands, bringing new questions and problems to these lands, and thus new ethical challenges that did not exist before (Moor, 1985). The fascinating possibilities offered by the technology of the future in the field of education have a similarly enormous potential. But good and bad, evil and sacred always come in a mixed package (Johnson & Miller, 2008).

It is clear that all the AI innovations that have entered our lives will not only offer great opportunities and gains in educational organizations but will also create very serious problems that our educational administrators and teachers have never encountered before and that educational administrators will need new skills to cope with these novice situations. Besides, the inclusion of a technological leader to coordinate technology in the school is more crucial than equipping schools with technological infrastructure to ensure the integration of technology (Anderson & Dexter, 2005). Leaders in the educational field will be able to advance scholastic technology to an unprecedented level by using modern techniques to inspire and manage team members (Puckett, 2014).

Addressing issues of AI Research in Educational Leadership over a wide spectrum, notably AI and immersive technologies in K–12 schools, school systems, and higher education, is the main goal of articles published in the AI Research in Educational Leadership. AIREL which is an online, open-access, and free journal publishes two issues a year.

With a focus on AI based technological implications for and enactments in the global world, AIREL welcomes researchers from all perspectives to participate in a debate on the effects of education digitalization over educational leadership and management. It seeks papers that demonstrate how the rising use of AI and immersive technologies associates with and influences all areas of educational administration, including policy and decision-making, legal regulations, and financing, through empirical as well as conceptual research. It also

encourages submissions that examine how AI and metaverse technologies mobilise and reflect global policies, discourses and trends in education, and how the digitalisation of education has positive educational and managerial implications as well as negative impacts, such as how it is linked to power inequalities and injustices within and between nations.

To be more precise, we encourage papers that explore the benefits, drawbacks, and morality of AI such as chatbots and algorithms, the implications of AI and immersive technologies in classrooms, how educational leaders will require to change to keep up with social and technological transformations based on AI, how educational administration should react to our changing globe, and so on.

The editors of AIREL encourage a variety of submissions, including theoretical and empirical articles as well as systematic literature reviews. In addition, the editors welcome papers based on partnerships among researchers, practitioners, decision-makers, and other stakeholders, using any methodology as long as it is credible and adheres to ethical research standards. It is highly encouraged that submissions draw on theories, conceptual frameworks, and original approaches from different disciplines.

References

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